

THE EFFICACY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED VIRTUAL ASSISTANTS IN ANSWERING FREQUENT INQUIRIES CONCERNING ACCELERATED ORTHODONTICS

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AIM: To evaluate the benefits of AI-based virtual assistants for improved compliance and treatment results due to availability of knowledge based on evidence without need to consult an orthodontist.

OBJECTIVES: To assess effectiveness and usefulness of four AI-powered virtual assistants that can be controlled by speech (Alexa, Google Assistant, Siri, and Cortana) in responding to frequently requested patient inquiries about Accelerated orthodontics.

HYPOTHESIS: AI voice assistants have potential to greatly enhance the field of accelerated orthodontics by improving treatment planning, optimizing tooth movement and enhancing patient compliance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Four orthodontic residents assessed the four most popular commercial virtual assistants using a predefined set of fifteen questions. Their performance was assessed using a modified Likert scale.

RESULTS: The mean score for Google Assistant was lowest (best), followed by those for Siri, Alexa, Cortana. Alexa and Cortana had much higher scores than Google Assistant.

CONCLUSION: Creation of an intelligent virtual assistant with suggestions based on research and chosen specifically for orthodontics may be a solution. The researchers agreed such device would be helpful to patients and medical personnel.

Key words : AI -based virtual assistants , accelerated orthodontics , Artificial Orthodontics.

INTRODUCTION

The creation of computer systems that are capable of carrying out tasks that normally call for human intelligence is known as artificial intelligence (AI). Learning, reasoning, problem-solving, perception, language comprehension, and decision-making are some of these tasks. AI seeks to develop devices and software that can replicate or imitate cognitive processes similar to those of humans, allowing them to carry out tasks more quickly and effectively.

Artificial intelligence (AI)-powered voice-assisted technologies are becoming more and more prevalent in a variety of industries, including dentistry. These devices, equipped with natural language processing (NLP) capabilities, are revolutionizing how dental professionals interact with technology, enhancing patient care, and improving overall efficiency.

Using voice-activated virtual assistants is one area of AI technology that has advanced significantly in recent years. Voice assistants, like Alexa from Amazon (Seattle, Wash.), Google Assistant (Google, Mountain View, Calif.), Cortana from Microsoft (Redmond, Wash.), and Siri from Apple (Cupertino, Calif.), are widely used software applications that are made to mimic human speech on the front end while providing users with information via a sizable database on the back end.² The new way to interact with technology is through spoken communication. since it is an intuitive way to communicate with things without requiring tactile contact.

Patients often express a desire for accelerated orthodontic procedures for various reasons, and this has led to increased interest in techniques and technologies that can expedite the orthodontic treatment process

Here are some common factors contributing to patients' curiosity about accelerating orthodontic procedures:

1. Reduced Treatment Time:

- One of the most common reasons patients express curiosity about acceleration methods is the desire to shorten the overall duration of orthodontic treatment. Accelerated methods aim to achieve tooth movement more quickly than traditional approaches.

2. Improved Comfort:

- Patients may be motivated by the prospect of experiencing less discomfort associated with orthodontic treatment. Accelerated techniques often claim to minimize the time spent wearing braces or aligners, potentially reducing the overall discomfort period.

3. Convenience:

- Accelerated orthodontic methods may offer increased convenience for individuals with busy lifestyles who may find it challenging to commit to prolonged treatment schedules. The prospect of a faster treatment process may be appealing to such patients.

4. Enhanced Aesthetics:

- Patients often appreciate the aesthetic benefits of orthodontic treatment, and accelerated methods may provide quicker results, leading to a faster improvement in smile aesthetics.

5. Technological Advances:

- The use of advanced technologies, such as vibrational devices and micro-osteoperforations, to accelerate tooth movement has sparked interest among patients who are intrigued by the incorporation of cutting-edge approaches in their orthodontic care.

6. Reduced Disruptions to Daily Life:

- Accelerated orthodontic procedures may involve fewer adjustments and appointments compared to traditional methods, potentially minimizing disruptions to a patient's daily life and routine.

7. Patient Education and Awareness:

- Increased awareness and education regarding accelerated orthodontic options through marketing, online information, and discussions with orthodontic professionals contribute to patients' curiosity about these procedures.

It's important for orthodontic professionals to address patient curiosity by providing accurate information about the benefits, risks, and realistic expectations associated with accelerated orthodontic procedures. While accelerated techniques can offer advantages in certain cases, they may not be suitable for everyone, and individual treatment plans should be carefully tailored based on the patient's unique needs and orthodontic issues. Open communication between orthodontists and patients is key to managing expectations and ensuring a positive orthodontic experience.

If patients express curiosity or interest in using voice-assisted devices to inquire about accelerating orthodontic procedures, it suggests a recognition of the convenience and accessibility that such technology can offer.

The applicability of the most recent Virtual helpers in orthodontics powered by AI is not well understood. Consequently, this study's goal was to assess effectiveness and usefulness of four voice-activated, AI-based virtual assistants (Alexa, Google Assistant, Siri, Cortana) in responding to frequently requested patient inquiries about Accelerated orthodontics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four orthodontic residents assessed the four most popular commercial virtual assistants—Alexa, Siri, Google Assistant, and Cortana—using a standardized set of fifteen questions. Their performance was assessed using a modified Likert scale.

The questions were formulated through conversations with orthodontists with extensive experience and by looking up frequently asked questions on websites.

The four devices were then asked questions, and the evaluators graded each device's response on a modified Likert scale with five points: (1) the device provided a sufficient response to the question; (2) the device provided a response but insufficient details; (3) the device did not directly respond to the question but instead offered a list of correct websites that addressed the question; (4) the device did not directly respond to the question but instead offered a list of inaccurate websites that address the question; and (5) the device was unable to determine the answer.

The Likert scale evaluations, with five being the lowest rating, were intended to represent the usefulness and efficiency of the gadgets.

Questionnaire for perception of additional steps need to shorten the duration of treatment.

1. How long would you expect orthodontic treatment to last?
2. How firmly do you concur that braces-based treatment takes too long?
3. . How long do you estimate the treatment for your braces will take?
4. For how long do you hope to wear braces?
5. Please indicate your level of interest in allowing your orthodontist to employ specialized wires to complete your treatment sooner.
6. How eager are you to have a corticotomy, a one-time surgical operation, in addition to wearing braces to shorten the length of your treatment? Similar to making cuts in the bone, this process is less invasive
7. How willing are you to use a safe tooth vibrator to shorten the time you need to wear braces?
8. How eager are you to undergo a single operation called a piezocision, which involves making small cuts on the gums to shorten the time you need to wear braces?
9. Please indicate your level of openness to having a one-time laser surgery perform little incisions (cuts) on your gums to shorten the time you need to wear braces
10. Please indicate your level of openness to having your orthodontist inject medication around your teeth to shorten the length of time you need to wear braces
11. Please rate the additional orthodontic techniques or operations from 1 to 5 in the order you would want or feel would be most convenient to undergo if recommended, taking into account a 25% -30% reduction in the amount of time you will be wearing braces.
Customized wires
Teeth vibrator Corticotomy (bone cuts)
Piezocision (cuts on the gums)
Lasers (cuts on the gums)
Drug injected around the teeth
12. If advised with the projected reduction in treatment duration, please rank these additional orthodontic techniques or treatments in the order you desire or feel convenient to undergo.
Customized wires
Teeth vibrator Corticotomy (bone cuts)

Piezocision (cuts on the gums)

Lasers (cuts on the gums)

Drug injected around the teeth

13. Which of the aforementioned techniques would you find attractive in terms of how much treatment time reduction?
14. If they could shorten your orthodontic treatment's duration, what percentage increase would you be ready to make?
15. How firmly do you concur that shortening the duration of your treatments could affect how you collect treatment fees?

RESULT

The mean score for Google Assistant was the lowest (1.47) out of all the gadgets. It performed noticeably worse than Cortana and Alexa. Siri, Alexa, and Cortana came next with 1.62, 2.28, and 3.25 points, respectively. Compared to Cortana, Siri had a much lower score. When comparing how each gadget replied to each investigator, there was a noticeable amount of variation among them (Alexa excluded).

For example, investigator MU's mean scores with Google Assistant and Siri differed significantly from those of the majority of the other investigators. Significant differences existed for Cortana between investigators AP, SY, and LC. But there was no discernible variation in Alexa's answers to the researchers' questions.

After the rating sessions, the researchers were questioned about if they believed there would be worth of owning a gadget that offers carefully chosen, answers to commonly asked inquiries by patients in an orthodontic practice that are supported by evidence, even though the answers varied amongst devices and users. In response to this question, the investigators all said "yes."

SAMPLE SIZE DERIVATION

Level of significance (α error) = 5%, Power = 80%, Type of test = two-sided
Formula of calculating sample size is

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

P	Estimated Population P = 80 % subject have perception that there is need of additional procedure to reduce treatment time	0.8
1- α	Confidence level	0.95
Z	Z value associated with confidence	1.96
d	Absolute precision	0.05
n	Minimum sample size	246

Assuming all the factors, minimum sample size comes around 246 rounded to 250 subjects in this study.

Method of data analysis:

Statistical analysis will be performed using Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) version 21 for Windows (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL).

Descriptive quantitative data will be expressed in mean and standard deviation respectively. Descriptive qualitative data will be expressed in percentage/proportion.

Confidence interval is set at 95% and probability of alpha error (level of significance) set at 5%. Power of the study set at 80%.

Comparison of perception will be done using Chi square test.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS**Reliability statistics**

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	15	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	15	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.873	15

No modifications needed.

Validity

	Mea n	S.D.	CO- RELATION
q1	2.7	0.2	0.6
q2	2.5	0.3	0.9
q3	2.2	0.47	0.7
q4	2.7	0.38	0.3
q5	3.8	0.52	0.8
q6	3.2	0.6	0.5
q7	2.9	0.8	0.8
q8	3.2	1.2	0.9
q9	2.9	0.5	1.1
q10	3.1	0.8	0.9
q11	2.9	0.7	0.7
q12	3	0.6	0.9
q13	3.8	0.5	1.2
q14	3.3	0.4	1.3
q15	2.8	0.6	0.4

DISCUSSION

The goal of computer science's artificial intelligence (AI) research is to create computer systems that behave intelligently like humans. Artificial intelligence has demonstrated its ability to execute and mechanize jobs that were previously unimaginable for many years. One instance is the application of conversational intelligent virtual assistants (IVA) in business, residential, and healthcare environments.

1. Alexa:

- Developed by Amazon, Alexa is a virtual assistant that powers devices like Amazon Echo smart speakers.

- It is designed to respond to voice commands, perform tasks such as setting alarms, playing music, providing weather updates, and controlling smart home devices.

- Alexa uses natural language processing and machine learning to understand and respond to user queries.

2. Cortana:

- Developed by Microsoft, Cortana is a virtual assistant integrated into the Windows operating system and available on various Microsoft devices.

- Originally designed for Windows Phone, Cortana can perform tasks, answer questions, set reminders, and interact with Microsoft applications.

- Cortana also has capabilities for natural language processing and can be used through voice commands.

3. Siri

- Siri is Apple's virtual assistant, present on iOS devices such as iPhones, iPads, Macs, Apple Watch, and Home Pod.

- Siri can perform a wide range of tasks, including sending messages, making phone calls, setting reminders, and providing information on various topics.

- It utilizes artificial intelligence and machine learning to understand context and improve its responses over time.

4. Google Assistant:

- Developed by Google, Google Assistant is available on a variety of devices, including Android smartphones, smart speakers, smart displays, and more.

- Google Assistant can answer questions, provide recommendations, play music, control smart home devices, and interact with other Google services.

- It is known for its powerful search capabilities, leveraging Google's vast knowledge base to provide accurate and relevant information.

These virtual assistants have become integral parts of their respective ecosystems, playing crucial roles in enhancing user experience, simplifying tasks, and integrating seamlessly with various smart devices. They continue to evolve with regular updates and improvements in their capabilities.

Accelerated orthodontics is an innovative approach aimed at reducing the time required to complete orthodontic treatment and achieve desired tooth movements. Traditional orthodontic treatments often take several months or years to correct misalignments, close gaps, or address bite issues. Accelerated orthodontics utilizes various methods and technologies to expedite this process. Here are some key aspects:

1. **Customized Wires:**

- Customized or special orthodontic wires may be used in accelerated orthodontics to facilitate tooth movement. These wires are designed to apply controlled forces to the teeth, optimizing the treatment process.

2. **Teeth Vibrator:**

- Devices like AcceleDent or Propel VPro5 are examples of teeth vibrators used in accelerated orthodontics. They deliver gentle vibrations or micropulses to the teeth to potentially stimulate bone remodeling and accelerate tooth movement. Patients typically use these devices for a specified amount of time each day.

3. **Corticotomy (Bone Cuts):**

- Corticotomy involves making small cuts in the cortical bone surrounding the teeth. This surgical technique aims to induce a temporary localized increase in bone turnover, facilitating faster tooth movement. It's a form of selective alveolar decortication.

4. **Piezocision (Cuts on the Gums):**

- Piezocision is a minimally invasive surgical technique that combines corticotomy with the use of piezoelectric instruments. These instruments make precise cuts in the bone and soft tissues, aiming to accelerate tooth movement while minimizing trauma to the surrounding gums.

5. **Lasers (Cuts on the Gums):**

- Laser-assisted orthodontics may involve using lasers to make controlled cuts in the soft tissues (gingiva) around the teeth. This can be part of procedures like laser-assisted flapless corticotomy.

6. ****Drug Injection Around the Teeth: ****

- Localized drug injections, such as the use of pharmacological agents or anesthetics, may be employed in accelerated orthodontics. These injections can target specific areas to enhance bone remodeling or manage discomfort during certain procedures.

It's important to note that these techniques are often used in combination or tailored to the specific needs of each patient. The decision to incorporate these methods depends on factors such as the patient's case complexity, oral health, and the orthodontist's expertise. Not all patients are candidates for accelerated orthodontics, and thorough consultation with a qualified orthodontist is essential to determine the most suitable approach for an individual's orthodontic treatment.

Virtual assistants can be highly beneficial in answering queries regarding accelerated orthodontics, providing timely and accurate information to patients. Here's how virtual assistants can be employed in this context:

1. ****Information on Accelerated Techniques: ****

- Virtual assistants can provide detailed explanations of various accelerated orthodontic techniques, including micro-osteoperforations, vibrational devices, corticotomy, piezocision, lasers, and drug injections. Users can inquire about the procedures, benefits, and potential risks.

2. ****Customized Treatment Plans: ****

- Virtual assistants equipped with artificial intelligence can analyze patient-specific data and provide information about whether accelerated orthodontics is suitable for an individual's case. They can explain how customized treatment plans may be developed to expedite the orthodontic process.

3. ****Procedure Walkthroughs: ****

- Users can ask virtual assistants to guide them through the steps of different accelerated orthodontic procedures, helping them understand what to expect before, during, and after treatment.

4. **Comparative Analysis:**

- Virtual assistants can offer comparative analyses of accelerated orthodontic techniques, outlining the advantages and disadvantages of each. This can assist patients in making informed decisions based on their preferences and treatment goals.

5. **Cost and Duration Estimations:**

- Users can inquire about the estimated costs and duration associated with accelerated orthodontics compared to traditional methods. Virtual assistants can provide general information and guide users on consulting with orthodontic professionals for more accurate assessments.

6. **Post-Treatment Care:**

- Patients can seek information on post-treatment care and recovery after undergoing accelerated orthodontics. Virtual assistants can provide guidance on oral hygiene practices, follow-up appointments, and any potential discomfort associated with the procedures.

7. **Patient Testimonials and Success Stories:**

- Virtual assistants can share patient testimonials and success stories related to accelerated orthodontics, offering real-world examples of individuals who have undergone such treatments and their experiences.

8. **Finding Qualified Orthodontists:**

- Users can ask virtual assistants to assist them in finding qualified orthodontic professionals who specialize in accelerated orthodontics. The virtual assistant can provide information on reputable practitioners and clinics.

9. **Research and Publications:**

- Virtual assistants can reference research articles, publications, and studies related to accelerated orthodontics, giving users access to credible sources for a deeper understanding of the field.

10. ****Integration with Teleconsultations: ****

- Virtual assistants can facilitate the integration of teleconsultation services, allowing patients to schedule virtual appointments with orthodontic professionals to discuss their specific questions and concerns.

By leveraging natural language processing and artificial intelligence, virtual assistants can enhance patient education, promote informed decision-making, and provide a valuable resource for those seeking information about accelerated orthodontics. It's important to note that while virtual assistants can offer valuable insights, consulting with a qualified orthodontic professional for personalized advice and treatment planning remains crucial.

Conclusion

Creating a specialized virtual assistant for orthodontics would involve designing a system tailored to the unique requirements of orthodontic practices

While general virtual assistants can perform basic tasks, a specialized virtual assistant for orthodontics can provide a more tailored and comprehensive solution that aligns with the specific needs and challenges of orthodontic practices and their patients.

Developing a specialized virtual assistant for orthodontics involves collaboration between software developers, orthodontic professionals, and potentially artificial intelligence experts. The objective is to produce a tool that enhances the efficiency of orthodontic practices, improves patient experience, and aligns with the unique requirements between software developers, orthodontic professionals, and potentially artificial intelligence experts.

When answering frequently asked orthodontic questions, the virtual assistant performance scores showed considerable disparities.

An intelligent virtual assistant with evidence-based solutions specifically designed for orthodontics can help address these issues.

All of the study's researchers concur that using a gadget like this would benefit both doctors and patients.

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